

RESULTS

Fig. 1 shows the results of modeling the territory of potential distribution of *I. pavlovskyi* worldwide for three twenty-year periods of the second half of the 20th and early 21st centuries (1961-1980, 1981-2000, 2001-2020). As can be seen, areas of high suitability for this tick are located in Eurasia and North America. There are no suitable regions in the southern hemisphere. Comparison of this map with the map of spatial distribution of MESS (Multivariate Environmental Similarity Surfaces; Elith et al. 2010) values (Fig. 2) shows that areas with high suitability for *I. pavlovskyi* correspond to areas with positive MESS values, which indicates the correctness of the conclusions about the possibility of distribution of the studied species in these regions.

Fig. 3 shows the geographic distribution of the standard deviation (STD) of modeled suitability for the habitat of *I. pavlovskyi* worldwide, as a measure of modeling uncertainty. As can be seen, the overall STD does not exceed the value of 0.1. This demonstrates a low level of uncertainty in the results of the constructed model.

As shown in Fig. 1, North America has extensive areas of potential distribution of *I. pavlovskyi* tick in the northern United States and much of Canada. Currently there are no known finds of this species on that continent. According to the constructed model, no significant changes have been observed in the territory of potential distribution of *I. pavlovskyi* in North America in recent decades. However, the western part of the potential North American climatic range of *I. pavlovskyi* has become somewhat less suitable for the habitation of this species in recent decades.

Fig. 1. Geographic distribution of the habitat suitability of *I. pavlovskyi* worldwide for three twenty-year study periods from 1961 to 2020 according to the constructed model.

Fig. 2. Geographic distribution of the MESS values for three twenty-year study periods from 1961 to 2020.

Fig. 3. Geographic distribution of standard deviation of suitability for *I. pavlovskiy* for three twenty-year study periods from 1961 to 2020 according to the constructed model.

Fig. 4. Geographic distribution of the habitat suitability of *I. pavlovskiy* in Eurasia for three twenty-year study periods from 1961 to 2020 according to the constructed model.

Fig. 4 shows a detailed map of the potential distribution area of *I. pavlovskyi* in Eurasia. In general, as can be seen, most of the detection points are located in areas with high suitability of climatic conditions for tick habitation. Along with them, the model also identifies a number of large areas for the possible distribution of *I. pavlovskyi*, where this species has not been found to date. According to the constructed model, the main part of the potential distribution area of *I. pavlovskyi* is located in Russia.

The most significant changes during the period under study occurred in the Siberian region of the potential range of *I. pavlovskyi* (Fig. 4). There is a significant expansion of this territory to the north, northwest, and especially to the northeast – towards the eastern part of the tick's range. There are also separate areas of its expansion in the southern direction.

In the period 1961-1980, the area of relatively high suitability for *I. pavlovskyi* (more than 0.4) in the Siberian region generally coincides with the data on its actual distribution. A small area of moderate suitability (0.4-0.5) without actual records is located in the area of the city of Bratsk in the Irkutsk region (Russian Federation) (Fig. 4). Also, to date, the species has not been found in the western part of Lake Baikal, although the model reveals small areas of fairly high suitability of climatic conditions for *I. pavlovskyi* to live here – on the northern shore of Lake Baikal in the Irkutsk region around the city of Irkutsk (up to 0.9) and on the southern shore of Baikal in the Republic of Buryatia (Fig. 4). In the period 1981-2000, these two areas slightly increase both in size and in the degree of suitability for *I. pavlovskyi*. However, the most significant changes in the potential range of the tick species under study in these areas are observed in 2001-2020. There is a very significant expansion of the main part to the east, which now covers the city of Bratsk. The suitability here reaches values from 0.9 to 1. In the west of Lake Baikal, the potential geographic range greatly expands in its northern part in the area of the city of Irkutsk, practically merging with the area around the city of Bratsk. The southern border of this part of the potential range of *I. pavlovskyi* shifts significantly to the south, reaching the border of Mongolia (Fig. 4).

In the southern Siberian part of the potential distribution of *I. pavlovskyi*, there is also a gradual, period-by-period increase in the area of high suitability in a south-eastern direction on the territory of the Republic of Tyva (Russian Federation), which expands in the form of a tongue towards its capital, Kyzyl (Fig. 4). A particularly strong increase in the suitability for habitation of the species *I. pavlovskyi* in this region occurs in the period 2001-2020, although there are no data on the detection of the studied tick species here (Fig. 4). Otherwise, the southern boundary of this area remains virtually unchanged.

In the period 2001-2020, an increase in the Siberian part of the potential range of *I. pavlovskiyi* in the north-west direction, in the area of the cities of Novosibirsk and Tomsk, is also observed, compared to previous periods. The degree of suitability for the habitation of *I. pavlovskiyi* in the northern part of the Kemerovo region (around the city of Kemerovo and further north) increases as well. It was during this period that information appeared about the discovery of this species in these areas, which had not been previously found there (Grigoryeva and Livanova 2012; Livanova et al. 2016; Mikryukova et al. 2014; Kovalev et al. 2015; Tkachev et al. 2017; Nikoshenko and Zubova 2021). This is consistent with the results of our modeling (Fig. 4).

Thus, the results of our modeling indicate a significant improvement in climatic conditions for the life of the studied species and an increase in the likelihood of its spread in the Siberian region in the 21st century.

The constructed model reveals, throughout all three periods, an area of high suitability for the possible habitation of the *I. pavlovskiyi* tick much further west than its main range – in the southern Ural region, between the cities of Yekaterinburg, Chelyabinsk and Ufa. In the period 1981-2000, this zone, compared to the period 1961-1980, expands to the east, reaching the city of Tyumen, and also to the north and northwest, reaching the city of Perm (Fig. 4). By 2001-2020, there is some reduction in this part of the *I. pavlovskiyi* potential range in the northern and northwestern direction, while in the eastern direction there is a significant expansion and almost merging with the West Siberian region of both potential and actual habitat of the *I. pavlovskiyi* tick. This new territory affects the Omsk region, where the tick has not yet been found, as well as large areas in northern Kazakhstan, including its capital, Astana (Fig. 4). However, currently there are no finds in this part of Kazakhstan.

In the other territory of Kazakhstan, *I. pavlovskiyi* was discovered back in the 1960s in its eastern part, in the Western Altai (Filippova and Ushakova 1967). Other areas of possible distribution in Central Asia, where there are finds of this tick, are located in the east of Kyrgyzstan and in the southeast of Kazakhstan – in the Dzungarian Alatau Mountains (Ushakova et al. 1976) and on the western spurs of the Tien Shan Mountains (Livanova et al. 2016; Fedorova 2017; Fedorov and Hornok 2024). These areas extend into the territory of the northwestern regions of China, where one find of *I. pavlovskiyi* was made in 1973 (Guo et al. 2016). According to the constructed model, the areas of possible distribution of *I. pavlovskiyi* in this region change insignificantly over the studied periods (Fig. 4). The constructed model also reveals an area with high suitability for the possible distribution of *I. pavlovskiyi* in the west of Kyrgyzstan and in the north and center of Tajikistan, where *I. pavlovskiyi* has not yet been found. Changes in the potential range over the studied periods in these areas are insignificant (Fig. 4).

The modeling results reveal two areas of possible distribution of the studied species in the Caucasus, where there are no data on its detection. The first area is located in the northern Caucasus, on the border of Russia and Georgia. The second area is located in the southern Caucasus, at the junction of Georgia, Armenia and Turkey. Temporal changes in the potential range of *I. pavlovskyi* in these areas are insignificant.

The model constructed for the period 1961-1980 identifies areas of moderate suitability (0.4-0.5) in the Moscow and Nizhny Novgorod regions, although *I. pavlovskyi* was not found there. In subsequent study periods, the suitability for tick habitation in these areas significantly decreases (Fig. 4).

In the Russian Far East, the area of high habitat suitability for *I. pavlovskyi*, according to our modeling, occupies the south of Khabarovsk Krai and almost the entire Primorsky Krai, where this species was discovered in both the 20th and 21st centuries (Filippova and Beliaev 1970; Kolonin 1986; Nikitin et al. 2015). It also includes the coast of the Sea of Japan, where currently there is no information on the discovery of this species (Fig. 4).

Our model also reveals an area of high suitability for the *I. pavlovskyi* tick in the eastern part of the potential range, in northeastern China and North Korea. This area has undergone a slight northward expansion in 2001–2020 (Fig. 4). There are no records of *I. pavlovskyi* in North Korea, but in northeastern China it was found in Dunhua County on a sample dated 1959 (Guo et al. 2016). This find corresponds to the area of relatively high habitat suitability for *I. pavlovskyi* detected by the model. Another record of this species in the northernmost part of northeastern China was made in 1996 (Takada et al. 1998), but this point does not fall within the potential range of the tick revealed by the model. In China, in addition to the indicated areas of high suitability for *I. pavlovskyi* habitat in the northwest and northeast, the constructed model identifies another area in the southwest, in Tibet on the border with Nepal. However, the studied tick species has not been detected here to date. Temporal changes in this area are insignificant (Fig. 4).

In Japan, the area of possible distribution of *I. pavlovskyi*, according to the constructed model, occupies almost the entire territory of Hokkaido Island (Fig. 4), where there are reports of detection of this tick species (Nakao et al. 1992). In addition, two small areas of high suitability were identified in the north and in the center of Honshu Island, where the *I. pavlovskyi* tick, according to available data, has not been detected to date (Fig. 4). Changes in the areas of possible distribution of *I. pavlovskyi* in Japan during the studied periods are insignificant.

Table 1 shows the importance values of bioclimatic parameters for constructing a model of the possible distribution of *I. pavlovskyi* according to four types of tests provided by MaxEnt software. These values are averaged over the simulation results for 20 sets of background points.

Table 1. The importance of bioclimatic parameters for modeling the possible spread of *I. pavlovskyi* in four tests (the colors indicate the ranks of the parameters in each test: red – first rank, yellow – second rank, green – third rank, blue – fourth rank, white – fifth rank).

Bioclimatic parameter	Contribution	Permutation importance	Training gain with only parameter	Training without gain parameter	Overall importance ranking
BIO1	44.1457	35.2971	0.647	1.0009	1
BIO2	3.0162	7.0836	0.1518	1.3222	5
BIO4	16.2307	14.4566	0.2715	1.231	4
BIO12	12.0208	18.6011	0.3567	1.0659	3
BIO15	24.5866	24.5616	0.3761	1.1144	2

As can be seen in this table, the most important parameter according to all tests is BIO1 (annual mean temperature). The second most important parameter according to three tests is BIO15 (precipitation seasonality). The third place according to two tests is BIO12 (annual precipitation). The fourth place is BIO4 (temperature seasonality). The least important parameter according to the results of all tests is BIO2 (mean diurnal range).

Fig. 5 shows the response curves of 5 bioclimatic parameters, reflecting the reaction of the suitability for habitation to the value of the bioclimatic parameter. The response curves are constructed in two ways: 1) when calculating the model, the values of all parameters except the one under study are set to the average value for the samples (upper row in Fig. 5); 2) the model is constructed for only one parameter under study (lower row in Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. Response curves of the bioclimatic parameters. The top row is response curves for parameters keeping all other parameters at their average sample values, the bottom row is response curves created using only one parameter. The curves are based on the results of model runs on 20 sets of background points. The red color indicates average values, and the gray areas indicate 90% percentiles of the scatter.

Comparing Fig. 5 and Table 1, we can see that the least uncertainty in the response curves is observed for the parameters that are most important for constructing the model. Also, the degree of importance of the parameter corresponds to the degree of visual similarity of the curves in the two methods of obtaining them. It is clear that all parameters, except for BIO2, are characterized by the presence of areas of their low values to the right and left of the interval with high suitability for the species to live in. This may indicate that the modeled ecological niche reflects the fundamental niche to a high degree, since in the feature space, the points of the geographic space with low suitability projected into it seem to surround the area of points with high suitability on all sides without forming open edges. The presence of such open edges of the modeled niche is associated with high uncertainty of the model, since part of the fundamental niche may end up in an area that is absent in the analyzed geographic space. This, in turn, may lead to a high probability of errors in identifying potential distribution areas of a species where it is not found, and in projecting the model to other climate situations, for example when simulating ranges under future climates (Brown and Carnaval 2019).

DISCUSSION

The preliminary selection of bioclimatic parameters using cluster analysis aimed to reduce the collinearity of predictors for modeling the distribution of *I. pavlovskyi* tick. As a result, five parameters were chosen from the five identified clusters. The BIO2 parameter was also selected as it

had a fairly weak correlation with other members of cluster 1. During the final selection, it was determined that excluding the BIO2 parameter reduced the final quality of the modeling, although it had the lowest importance for it. At the same time, the BIO8 parameter reduced the overall quality of the model. Apparently, these predictors, although they have a low overall importance for building the model, in certain aspects have a fairly strong influence on the final result of the modeling.

The constructed model of the *I. pavlovskyi* range generally identified the known distribution regions of this species in the Far East, Western Siberia and the Republic of Khakassia (Russian Federation), Japan, and the eastern regions of Kazakhstan and Kyrgyzstan. In addition, areas of high habitat suitability for this species were identified in territories where this species is currently not found. These are such regions of Russia as the Irkutsk Region, the south of Krasnoyarsk Krai, the western part of the Republic of Buryatia, the northern part of the Republic of Tuva, the Southern Ural, the Tyumen and Omsk Regions of Western Siberia, the North Caucasus (Russian Federation), as well as a small area on the border of Turkey and the Transcaucasian countries, Tajikistan and northern Afghanistan, western regions of Kyrgyzstan, northern Kazakhstan, certain regions of China in its northwest, northeast and in Tibet, the territory of North Korea and certain islands of Japan (Honshu Island). Some of these areas are adjacent to areas with already recorded habitat of the species, while other areas are located quite far from them.

According to the obtained results, the *I. pavlovskyi* tick has little potential for spreading in the territory of PRC. The largest area of its potential spread is in the northeast. However, only one of the three actual detection points of *I. pavlovskyi* is located in a region relatively close to the northeastern area of potential spread of this tick. It can be assumed that the range of *I. pavlovskyi* in China occupies a larger area, but the extremely small number of finds does not allow us to construct a model of the *I. pavlovskyi* geographic range in this region of Eurasia. Obviously, further efforts are needed to study the actual distribution of this species in China.

The data obtained as a result of the study indicate the need for additional monitoring of the state of acarofauna in regions of Eurasia that are included in the potential modeled range of the *I. pavlovskyi* tick in order to promptly identify this species dangerous to humans.

The constructed model showed a vast territory of potential habitat for *I. pavlovskyi* in North America. How real is the possibility of *I. pavlovskyi* invasion on this continent is a debatable issue. For example, studies have shown a fairly high invasive potential of the North American species *I. scapularis* in Eurasia, but to date this species has not been found on this continent (Zhang et al. 2022).

The modeling provided interesting data on changes in the potential range of the *I. pavlovskyi* tick over the three study periods (1961 to 2020), which are associated with the observed climate

changes. It is possible to note a significant difference between various regions of Eurasia in terms of the degree of change in the potential range of *I. pavlovskyi* over these periods. The greatest changes were found in the northwestern part of the tick's range – on the territory of Siberia in the Russian Federation. Here, a significant expansion of the potential distribution area of *I. pavlovskyi* in the 21st century was noted. The expansion occurs mainly in the western, northwestern, northern, northeastern and especially eastern directions. According to the constructed model, these changes may result in the formation of a single habitat of the *I. pavlovskyi* species from the Ural to Lake Baikal. Apparently, this is due to a significant improvement in the climatic conditions for the habitat of the studied tick species in these regions of Northern Asia, primarily due to an increase in their heat supply, which is demonstrated in the works (Third assessment report... 2022; Popova et al. 2018). These modeling results are also consistent with our studies to identify the most important criteria affecting the distribution of the *I. pavlovskyi* species. They showed that, according to all tests, the BIO1 (annual mean temperature) parameter is of the greatest importance, which is most relevant in cold regions and is, apparently, the main limiting factor here. The observed climate warming naturally leads to an expansion of the habitat boundaries of the studied species in the northern part of its range. This is confirmed by actual findings made in a number of areas that, according to the results of our modeling, fell into the zone of possible distribution of the *I. pavlovskyi* species – in the Tomsk and Novosibirsk regions and in the northern part of the Kemerovo region (Fig. 4), as already mentioned above.

The model we created also confirmed the realism of the information about the discovery of *I. pavlovskyi* in the Krasnoyarsk Territory at the beginning of the 21st century, at a considerable distance to the northeast of Krasnoyarsk. Thus, during the preparation of data on the finds of *I. pavlovskyi* individuals, in the reports obtained from the GBIF database, we identified a species detection point with coordinates 59.04° N and 98.67° E, dating back to 2005 and originating from GenBank (marked in Fig. 4 with the × sign). At the selection stage, this point was discarded as erroneous or as an accidental introduction, since it was located very far from other detection points. However, according to the constructed potential model range of *I. pavlovskyi* for 2001-2020, this point falls into the area of fairly high suitability (0.6-0.7). Based on these results, it can be stated with a high degree of certainty that this is a true discovery of *I. pavlovskyi*. Thus, this fact can also serve as confirmation of the already occurring significant expansion of the *I. pavlovskyi* range in this region, located quite far to the northeast of its known habitat.

In contrast to the northern, the southern boundary of the Siberian part of the potential range of the tick *I. pavlovskyi* changes less significantly, according to our modeling. The strongest change in the southern direction occurs in the mountainous regions of the Republic of Tyva, where the spread

may reach its capital, Kyzyl, and in the western Baikal region, where the area greatly expands to the south to the border with Mongolia. This may be a manifestation of the softening of the harsh mountain climate under the influence of the observed climate changes.

In other more southern areas of the *I. pavlovskyi* range (the Far East, Central and East Asia), the boundaries and degree of suitability of potential areas for the possible spread of the tick remain virtually unchanged over time and are similar for all three periods studied, which is obviously determined by the nature of climatic changes in these regions.

Using four methods offered by MaxEnt software, we assessed the importance of predictors for building a model of the *I. pavlovskyi* distribution. The parameter BIO1 (annual mean temperature) had the greatest importance by a large margin over other parameters, as noted above, according to all four tests. The relationship between the biological significance of climatic factors for the vital activity and distribution of organisms and their importance for building range models is a debatable issue, but in some cases such a relationship cannot be denied, especially with a very high assessment of model importance, as in this case. In general, it is obvious that temperature factors have a critical influence on the life of living beings (Popova and Popov 2013, 2019). Previous studies have shown the high importance of average annual temperatures for the formation of populations of *I. ricinus* and *I. persulcatus* ticks, related to *I. pavlovskyi* (Taiga tick... 1985; Sirotkin and Korenberg 2022).

The other two temperature parameters (BIO2 and BIO4), reflecting the monthly and annual variability of surface air temperature, were of least importance. However, as noted earlier, including BIO2 in the model significantly improves the overall quality of the resulting model.

The BIO15 (precipitation seasonality) parameter was second to BIO1 in importance for building the model, and BIO12 (annual precipitation) was third. It is worth noting that the BIO15 parameter, as it reflects the annual variability of the precipitation regime, is very important for the distribution model. This is probably due to the fact that, together with the BIO12 parameter, it shows, albeit indirectly, the amount of precipitation during the warm period of the year, when ticks are active. It is known that in temperate latitudes, the maximum precipitation occurs at the end of summer and the beginning of autumn, especially in the Far East, which is affected by the monsoon (Popov and Popova 2024). Parameters that directly show the amount of precipitation during this period of the year, such as BIO13 (precipitation of wettest month) or BIO18 (precipitation of warmest quarter), were not used for building the model, since they had a high correlation with BIO12 (Fig. 2).

Fig. 5 shows the response curves of the suitability for habitation to the values of the bioclimatic parameters. It can be seen that for the three parameters that showed the highest values for building the model (BIO1, BIO12 and BIO15) the curves obtained by both methods have a similar

shape. In the case of the other two parameters, the curves were quite different, especially for BIO2. We assume that this fact may reflect the importance of these parameters for building the model in some individual areas of the geographic space, while the most important factors have a total significance.

Using these curves, it is also possible to identify the values of climatic factors that limit the distribution of the studied species. In particular, Fig. 5 shows that for the average annual surface air temperature (parameter BIO1), the suitability range from 0.2 to 1 corresponds to parameter values between approximately -3°C and $+7^{\circ}\text{C}$. Previously, we identified the values of climatic factors that limit the distribution of the taiga tick *I. persulcatus* (Popov and Popova 2020). The maximum average annual temperature that limits the vital activity of the species *I. persulcatus* was 5.3°C , which is slightly lower than that required for the vital activity of the tick *I. pavlovskyi*. At the same time, as we established, the minimum annual precipitation required for the existence of *I. persulcatus* species is 339 mm. As seen in Fig. 5, for BIO12, this approximately corresponds to the suitability for habitation of *I. pavlovskyi* at 0.2-0.3. Thus, it can be argued that the lower limits of the needs of both species for this environmental factor coincide. These results may indicate both differences and similarities in the ecological requirements of the two related species.

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